

The use of interactive narration techniques in teaching history By:

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This article partially presents the results of the work of professor Leandro Villela de Azevedo in his research into the practical application of interactive narration techniques, arising from RPG games (RolePlaying Game) in elementary school students, in four schools in the State of São Paulo. Paul. Establishing the theoretical basis for such use and demonstrating their effectiveness, especially with regard to teaching attitudinal content, linked to the deepening of procedural and conceptual objectives.

RPG emerged as a form of entertainment in the United States in the 1970s. It is an interactive form of storytelling, where a main narrator takes on the role of the storyteller, while each of the participants takes on the role of role of a character within that narrative. Each participant can request actions only for their own characters, while the narrator controls all other characters (NPC – Nonplayable Character) and the result of actions in the universe being narrated. The participant can say that their character will try to open a door, for example, but it is up to the narrator to say whether this action was performed correctly, or whether the door was locked. This narrative technique has received several scientific studies both in the United States and in Brazil (RODRIGUES, 2004).

The use of the interactive narration technique for educational purposes began in Brazil at the end of the 90s, and in 2002 an NGO called Ludus Culturalis emerged, which organized four RPG and Education symposiums (2002, 2004, 2006, 2007) with a total of more than 3000

participants. The proceedings of the first of these symposiums were later edited by the publisher Devir.

Interactive narration can occur in different ways, but, for the purposes of better adapting to the content of this article, we will divide it into two categories. To the *regulated* and the *not regulated*. With the advent of RPGs, rule systems emerged that facilitated the creation of both the universe and story to be narrated, as well as the creation of the characters that would be played by the participants. Systems like *Dungeons and Dragons*, *GURPS*, *World of Darkness*, facilitated the creation of fantastic universes that could range from science fiction environments to dungeons infested with monsters or dragons, from werewolves and vampires to characters from Brazilian folklore (LIMA, 2006). These rule manuals are generally accompanied by data that help the narrator establish "chance" within his narration. For example, a participant indicates the desire for their character to walk across a tightrope. Within the entire context of the narration, this character proved to be athletic, but had never tried to cross a tightrope before. Thus, the narrator establishes that there is a 50% chance of this action being successful, thus establishing that on the six-sided die, a result equal to or less than three means that he will be able to carry out the action, otherwise he will fall from the rope. The narratives *not regulated*, depend much more on the imagination of the narrator himself, since at the same time it gives him much more freedom of creation, at the same time it establishes a more arbitrary narration, not leaving transparent the rules he uses for the success of actions, for example.

The first of these rule manuals created with an educational function appeared in Brazil around 2003, as a result of the joint effort of teachers participating in the aforementioned symposium. We have among them some focused on the history of Brazil, such as *The rescue of refugees* (where students take on the role of detectives who go in search of the painting *Retirantes* by Portinari, going through different aspects of the history of the painter and of Brazil in the first decades of the 20th century) or for general history, such as *The Crusades* (where the teacher can allow his students to simulate a religious war from the 13th century through interactive narration)

According to Cesar Coll and Antoni Zaballa (ZABALA, 1998, p.31) the teacher's objectives must encompass three types of content, conceptual, procedural and attitudinal. The first are the concepts themselves, typically called specific contents or subjects, such as *crusades, feudalism, etc.* The procedures refer to the *know how to do*, such as map interpretation, image analysis, among others. Finally, according to the author himself, the most challenging of these are the attitudinal ones, which refer to the *to be* that is, teaching students values that will be part of their character.

Interactive storytelling techniques allow for a deeper dive into each of the categories above, if they can be applied well. For example, the teacher creates a scenario relating to the colonization of Brazil, where students play different roles inside a caravel. This narration can extend over two or three classes, where different dangers will have to be experienced by them, such as calms and lack of food, such as storms, rats trying to feed on rare food, barrels of water that come loose and run out, diminish the little ones. available resources or even a disease, such as scurvy. During this first phase of the narration, they will be able to deepen their knowledge about the difficulties of navigation, in situations that they could never imagine until then, such as the possibility of dying of thirst surrounded by water. A simple list of these difficulties given by the teacher could not be understood with the degree of depth of seeing that your character could die during that difficulty, thus leaving him out of the activity, causing him to become emotionally involved with the story narrated, since I wouldn't want to stop participating in it.

In procedural terms, the possibility of a new, more practical meaning for the skills learned arises. Following the example above, the ability to read a map would be essential for the success of the adventure. The captains of the twelve vessels should meet and discuss, based on navigation charts, choosing the best route to reach their destination, avoiding storms and places of possible difficulties. More than that, it would be possible to work the opposite way. After arriving on dry land, on a second day of class, with the continuation of the narration, students could make their characters disembark on dry land, and leave

someone responsible for creating a map while they explored the unexplored Santa Cruz Island in this imagination guided by the teacher. This mapping would have to follow the instructions given, but could be a fundamental part of being able to return to the boats.

Still in procedural terms, it is more than feasible for some students to be responsible for writing a letter to King D. Manuel telling about their adventure in the new lands. Thus, before reading fragments of Caminha's letter, they would have their own report and elements of both reports could be compared. Thus working not only on the procedure for reading a historical document, but on the production of a report. I therefore understand the document more deeply when it is read.

The use of the interactive narration technique is efficient in deepening students' knowledge and may also be able to overcome some of the daily challenges faced by the teacher. According to the philosopher of education Edgar Morrin, there would be seven major challenges for the education of the future, according to his production made for UNESCO thinking about schools in the 3rd millennium (MORRIN, 1999).

The first of these challenges would be working with the *error* and the *illusion*. According to him, all knowledge, however scientific and careful it may be, is always subject to errors and therefore generating illusions. The biggest mistake would be to believe that knowledge is not subject to error and the biggest illusion would be to believe that it is possible to overcome all illusions. Within this basic principle, the practice of interactive narration allows the teacher to work on the issue of knowledge formation as a process and not absolute knowledge. According to the same established example of possible interactive narration, we would have a creation by the students that would be an account of their trip. Certainly, by critically analyzing the letter created by them, they would know that it does not reflect with absolute precision all the elements that they experienced, even though it may contain a relatively large amount of clues about how their adventure would have been.

In the same way that they could perceive the importance of this document for someone from outside to know how the interactive narration occurred in their classroom, they could also easily perceive that certain nuances were not faithfully described in the document, no matter how carefully the students who

created the letter have been. In this way, when comparing it with Caminha's letter, the teacher will find it easier to work with the idea of a historical document, even though it is indispensable for our better understanding of the past, it does not represent an absolute and infallible certainty of an event.

The example cited above allows the history teacher to work on the issue of documentation, which is, in a way, the essence of historical knowledge. Once there is the challenge that the student knows that while knowledge is important and scientific, it is not absolute, and that the history teacher knows that our historical knowledge came from the analysis of documents of the most diverse types, Both principles must be closely linked to each other. If it is impossible for the history teacher to create a scientific experiment that reproduces some experience, as would easily occur in the areas of biology, physics and chemistry, in interactive narration we have the possibility of the students creating and experiencing a fictitious history, but based on reality, where they can compare their actions with the documents they would produce, and thus have an idea of the other side of the coin. Since the historian's work, as a rule, always starts from the present, through documents, trying to understand the past and not the opposite, where people from one *present that has passed* they are living a situation and can perceive the result of the documents they created with the production of future knowledge about that time.

Still within the issue of error and illusion, interactive narration allows the teacher a new diagnostic evaluative dimension of their students. In a formal assessment, questions can generate a list of words and concepts, which, no matter how elaborate they may appear, can never have a practical dimension. While the students' reaction to a simulation imagined through interactive narration allows the teacher to see the "practical" use of those concepts. For example, returning to Portugal without an account of the religion of the indigenous people (because of the importance of religion at the time) or without an account of the riches and precious metals that could be found in this land (because of mercantilism and metalism) could be completely inappropriate. . However, since it is not an assessment

formal, the result of the non-practical use of a concept will not be in the form of a note, but rather in the form of an angry speech from the king (represented by the professor) due to the fact that the navigators did not bring the information he needed.

Still following Morrin's assumptions, we have the principles of the relevance of knowledge. Basically the idea that knowledge must be applied to practice, taking into account the microuniverse x macrouniverse and its complexity. Certainly, the discipline of history, to the extent that it allows us to think about the society around us, to understand and think about interventions, has full capacity to fulfill each of these assumptions. However, some specific concepts may take a few years of maturation before they can actually be applied in the student's life, such as the issue of participatory citizenship and critical reflection on society to generate community actions.

Interactive narration, however, allows, albeit in a simulated way, the student to intervene in an imaginary world, thus giving the opportunity for practical applications of knowledge that until then would only be possible at more advanced ages. At the same time, it allows the personal experience of experiencing a historical era. It is very common, in the field of history, for economic, social and political models little by little to replace personal narration, in a sensible attempt to demonstrate that history is not just in the hands of a few people who decided the destiny of all humanity. Although such thinking is correct with regard to the democratic formation of citizens, it can make action within microuniverses difficult, since, especially in older times, it is difficult to establish a non-generalist history of everyday life. Using interactive narration, the teacher allows the student to experience the role of a specific character, working on the issue of microhistory, at the same time that its reflection allows a more macro view and the establishment of models.

Morrin's third assumption is the teaching of Human Nature, in its various facets and aspects, allowing students to reflect on their own individual and collective existence. In a way, this item, combined with the practical issue of the previous item, can be linked to what Zabala calls

attitudinal content. So that the applicability of interactive storytelling techniques to achieve both objectives can be worked on together here.

By placing the student in a simulated situation through narration, the teacher can place them in situations of moral conflict, where they can not only argue in favor of a decision, but see the possible consequences of it. In the activity called *Cecília Sumiu* (AZEVEDO, 2007) students play characters who were hired to investigate the disappearance of Cecília, daughter of a Lord of Engenho. During the adventure, the students discover that she did not actually disappear, on the contrary, she helped some slaves escape and is now with them in a quilombo, of her own free will. At the moment this discovery is made, the overseer accompanied by some bush captains discover the quilombo and Cecília's whereabouts. It is then up to the students to decide the actions of their characters, which can range from trying to mediate the situation by avoiding a dispute, supporting the quilombo invasion, fighting to defend the fugitives, among others. When debating among themselves about a situation in which they have already been immersed for at least 40 minutes of narration, a series of moral and ethical aspects are raised. In a very similar way to what they will experience in adult life in different situations, whether in their professional or personal lives. Having the opportunity to experience these situations in practice and feel their possible consequences allows us to delve deeper into the issue of knowledge of human nature, both in terms of developing a critical or supportive attitude towards an event.

The fifth item raised by Morrin is living with uncertainty and positioning yourself in the face of it. Traditional history teaching sometimes leaves no room for uncertainty, as it deals with the study of the past. Even though some specific knowledge, such as the techniques that the Egyptians used to build their monuments, may still remain uncertain, this does not, in itself, characterize uncertainty in the students' lives. Morrin, in his work, uses history exactly to explain his idea of the uncertain. According to him, who would have been able to imagine at the beginning of the world war in 1914, that it would last for four years or that it would see a revolution?

socialism occur in Russia? Or who could have imagined that the terms that dictated the end of the First World War would help the emergence of a second one? Since students, when looking at the past, take the stance of an observer who already sees the results of actions, it is difficult for them to experience the uncertainties that people in their time had.

In a survey carried out with 100 elementary school students, in the 8th year, between 2005 and 2006, the author of this article asked the students the main doubt they had about the Napoleonic period. The most frequently raised doubt, by around 30% of the students, was the lack of understanding of what would have led Napoleon to want to attack Russia even in winter, since he should have already known that this would lead to an almost certain failure. It is common for us to attribute current knowledge and values to historical characters, making it difficult to understand their actions.

The interactive narration technique, by placing the student experiencing a historical character, allows them, before knowing the consequences of their actions, to make decisions based on knowledge of the time. After applying the activity in which students played Napoleon's assistants, practically everyone advised him to quickly invade Russia to increase his power. In this way demonstrating that there was a logic behind the French leader's actions. Regardless of Napoleon's specific question, we realize that interactive narration, by placing the student in the role of a character immersed in a certain situation or historical period, allows them to see as uncertainty something that is already considered past for us, experiencing moments of decisions and reinterpretations of the situation around them, helping them learn to deal with similar situations when they occur in their lives.

The sixth item raised by Morrin is understanding the other. The discipline of history plays an important role in this regard, as it introduces students to a diversity of peoples, cultures, belief systems and societies, which allow for the expansion of the student's cultural universe, coexistence with the different, respect and for sometimes even admiration from the other who until then was unknown to him. Although there are a series of elements of this discipline that allow us to work with the issue of otherness, interactive narration also expands the possibilities here.

Through the interactive narration technique, the student can not only understand the other, their culture, their beliefs, studying them from the outside, but they can also participate in the narration by interpreting the other, therefore having a character immersed in another culture. In this way we have an experience much more similar to the practice of that culture, where the student in a certain way becomes the other, experiencing situations that that person or society experiences or experienced, thus sharing elements of this new culture with which they are now in contact. . Literature and cinema already had, in a way, this ability, by allowing the reader/viewer to have a deeper insight into the thoughts and feelings of a given character, and to see the story from a particular point of view. Interactive narration, by introducing interaction and allowing the student to make their own decisions within the story, exponentially deepens this power, since they will not only see the actions and justifications through the explanation from a particular person's point of view, but also from From an initial situation created, the student himself will need to make his own decisions and verify their consequences according to the teacher's planning.

According to Morrin, this otherness would need to develop in two aspects, one more objective and intellectual, and the other more subjective and emotional. In a way, according to Zabala's division, one step would be to know what is different by following conceptual principles (it is possible to know an entire belief system of an Indian society, for example, knowing all the names of the castes, their functions, their origin and its ills) another level of knowledge would be the one that would bring about an attitudinal transformation in the student, where he, in addition to understanding that society as an object of study, would learn to respect it, taking an equal stance towards it, and not of superiority. Interactive narration, by allowing the student to experience the role of a character from another culture, facilitates the understanding of this second dimension, where there is not only an understanding of the other rationally, but an emotional involvement or development of respect for them.

Finally, Morrin brings us the issue of human ethics, establishing democracy and critical participatory citizenship as the focus of this ethics. The school environment provides many of these experiences to the student and the

History can often be their central focus. For example, holding assemblies, creating student groups, or even simple everyday items, such as students voting on whether or not a fan should be turned on in the room. Although interactive narration is not such an innovative element in this item, it allows the teacher to work on a series of issues related to it. In the initial example where students would play the crew of the 12 vessels of Cabral's expedition, for example, we discuss them to make decisions. It is not possible for each of the caravels to take a different position. Even though, historically speaking, the moment of great navigations is not at all democratic, the discussion between the students who represent each of the vessels can be. Their argumentation regarding each of the possible actions in the narration and the sharing of the consequences together, allows a series of discussions to emerge, which are the basis for a full democratic experience.

Below are transcripts of the student discussion regarding the activity *Cecília Sumiu*, previously mentioned:

Student 1: The boys want to be on the overseer's side, they only care about the money, but we want to support Cecília's decision, I think she must be in love with a slave and I love love stories.

Student 2: But if the issue is money, she is the daughter who owns the farm, she could ask her father to make the payment to them saying that the foreman was the one who started shooting while she was still with the blacks.

Student 3: Yes, but for that you would need to take her to Casa Grande, and her father would never let her leave there again.

Student 1: It's true, it remembers what the professor taught about the way women were treated at the time.

Student 4: She must have some jewelry with her, let's say that if she gives the jewelry we will side with her

Student 2: Do you want a bribe? Even here in the activity you are petty, huh.

Student 3: Yes, but what if we try to convince the overseer to pretend they didn't find her.

Student 4: But how would you do that? I'm not going to pay him anything.

Student 2: Let's tell her that the only way to help the slaves is to stay with us. So we get the reward, we share it with the overseer and the father won't even remember to capture the slaves.

Student 3 : Wait. I have an idea. What if the daughter says that she was captured by someone else and that the slaves fought to free her? Then we can convince the farm owner to let them go free as a reward for saving his daughter's life.

Student 4: And we still get our reward.

Student 1: But then she won't be able to live with the slaves?

Student 2: Yes, but you can't have everything, can you? Did you want it to end like Romeo and Juliet?

Student 1: All good. We decided.

Within the hypothetical scenario created by the teacher, the students needed to discuss the decision they were going to make that would change the fate of all their characters. They were emotionally connected to the story, transposing elements of it into their own lives. When discussing, they realized that the issue was much more about uniting ideas and proposing new actions, through each person's contribution, than just voting on previously established options. The subsequent discussion of these elements, mediated by the teacher, can be much more useful for students' understanding of the true meaning of democratic participation, than simply electing a class representative, as we see occurring in many schools. Argumentation with others allows the creation of new ideas and new courses of action, which are decided collectively, even if the final result may not completely please everyone, but there was a consensus.

Despite the advantages of using the interactive narration method, the technique still has little practical support in the area of education. The aforementioned NGO LudusCulturalis was closed at the end of 2009, and there were no new RPG and education Symposiums. Currently, Educational RPG workshops are still taking place at Centro Cultural São Paulo, organized by MegaCorp in partnership with Gibiteca Henfil.

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